

Analytical application of *p*-sulfonamidophenylazo-bis-acetoxime in the spectrophotometric determination of iron(III)

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p-Sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime has been used for spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) at 405 nm, keeping the pH at 2.5–3.0. Beer's law is obeyed in the range $(4 \text{ to } 24) \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are $1853 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 30.14 ng cm^{-2} , respectively.

The hydroxytriazenes are used for the determination of transition metals¹. We report here application of *p*-sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime (*p*-SPABA) for spectrophotometric determination of iron(III).

Results and discussion

Iron(III) was found to form 1 : 2 complex with *p*-sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime.

Harvey and Manning's method² and Purohit's method³ have been used to determine the stability constants. Validity of the methods can be confirmed from the value of $\log \beta$ obtained from both the methods. The $\log \beta$ values agree quite well (Table 1). Further, the precision studies were carried out by measuring the absorbance of 10 sets of solution containing 11.17 ppm of iron(III), and *p*-SPABA in 1 : 5 ratio, under optimum conditions. The absorbance was measured against reagent blank at working wavelength (405 nm). Iron was successfully determined at 11.17 ppm level with good precision.

Interference of several cations and anions in the determination of iron was studied at 10, 50 and 100 ppm level. Interference was studied using following 23 cations and anions, viz. Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Ba^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, SO_3^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} . It was seen that at 10 ppm level, Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ did not interfere, hence their interference was studied at 50 ppm level. Here Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- did not interfere. Still further it was seen that at 100 ppm level the following ions still did not interfere : Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- . However, tolerance of still higher concentration was not studied. Thus it can be seen that iron(III) can be determined even in presence of a number of interfering species present at 100 ppm level. Thus from the above studies it may be concluded that *p*-sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime can be used successfully for spectrophotometric determination of iron(III).

Table 1. Values of $\log \beta$ and ΔG by two different methods

Name of method	Reagents	Composition of complex	Concn. of complex $\times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$	E_{in}	E_S	α	$K_{inst.} \times 10^{-9}$	$\beta \times 10^8$	$\log \beta$	$\Delta G^* \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$
Harvey and Manning's method	<i>p</i> -Sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime	1 : 2	5	0.474	0.402	0.152	1.03	9.71	8.98	-12.38
Purohit's method	<i>p</i> -Sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime	1 : 2	5	1.820	1.612	0.114	7.00	1.42	8.15	-11.18
		1 : 2	5	0.910	0.805	0.115	1.72	5.84	8.76	-12.03

*At 27°.

Experimental

p-Sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime was prepared by the reported method⁴.

A 1.0×10^{-2} M solution of ferric nitrate nonahydrate (B.D.H.) was prepared in distilled water and to prevent hydrolysis a few drops of 1N nitric acid were added to it. The solution was standardized with EDTA. A 1×10^{-2} M solution of the reagent *p*-SPABA was prepared in acetone. Tris-buffer (2%, v/v) was prepared.

A Systronic 108 spectrophotometer and a Systronic 324 pH meter were used.

Method : Spectrum of *p*-sulfonamidophenylazobisacetoxime was measured in the wavelength region 387–460 nm against solvent blank. Iron and *p*-SPABA solutions were taken in 1 : 5 ratio and the spectrum of the iron complex was recorded against reagent blank in the range 387–460 nm. The working wavelength was found to be 405 nm. A set of solutions containing Fe^{III} and *p*-SPABA reagent in ratio 1 : 5 was prepared and pH was varied between 2 and 6. The pH range of constant maximum absorbance was found to be 2.5–3.0. Composition of the complex was determined by Job's method and moles ratio method of Yoe and Jones. The study revealed that composition of iron(III) complex is

1 : 2 ratio. Absorbance of a set of six solutions having Fe^{III}-to-*p*-SPABA in ratio of 1 : 5 was measured at the corresponding working wavelength against reagent blank. Beer's law was obeyed in concentration range $(4-24) \times 10^{-5}$ M. Interference of 23 cations and anions in the determination of iron was studied. To the set of solutions containing iron-to-reagent ratio 1 : 5, 10 ppm of different foreign ions were added at optimum conditions. Absorbance was measured against reagent blank. Those ions, which did not interfere at 10 ppm level, their interference was against studied at 50 ppm level. In case no or little change in absorbance was observed as compared to the absorbance without any foreign ion, then interference for those ions was studied again at 100 ppm level. However, tolerance of still higher concentration was not studied.

References

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